

AGRICULTURAL ELECTROSTATIC PESTICIDE SPRAY PUMP

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Abstract— In order to protect food and fiber crops against insects, disease and weed pests used agricultural chemicals such as insecticides, fungicides herbicides. With classical methods more chemical than theoretically needed is often applied due to the variability in field conditions and the need to ensure complete. In this case, 95% of the chemical applied can be wasted to the ground, for soil pollution, or at most 50% of mass transfer onto the desired plant. The project shows that electrostatic spraying can offers a possible solution to those environmental problems by reducing spray drift and improving coverage of chemical to target plant .In this project are presented principle of Electrostatic Spraying, the equipments, technological aspects and application. This system is available in large scale but we can implement in small scale also.

Keywords— Spray Pump; Electrode; Charging Circuit; High Voltage Circuit

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout the years, research has shown that pesticides drift causes damage to non-target organism. Sometimes drift from certain chemicals can be detected on susceptible plants and animals miles away. As farmers begin to realize the environmental impacts of some of the older practices in agriculture, they are demanding spray equipment that is more efficient and safer for the environment.

The first step in reducing spray drift in timing. The applicator must look at the temperature, humidity, and wind speed to see how these factors would affect the spread of the pesticides. Most agriculture chemicals are volatile at higher temperature. After consulting the pesticides label; this must be taken into account. Higher humidity is good to reduce the chances of small droplet evaporating and not hitting their target. Thirdly, wind can cause problems by blowing the droplets away from target and increase the chances of non-target organisms being damaged.

Technology can also play a part I reducing spray drift. A relatively new product that has made its way to the forefront in recent years are electrostatic spray technology .Along with reducing spray drift, this type of application equipment

can improve canopy penetration ,increase the under leaf coverage, and decrease the total volume per acre applied.

2. HISTORY

The heart of the air –assisted electrostatic sprayer is the “air atomizing –induction charging” nozzle which was invented at the university of Georgia.

Air and liquid enter the rear of the nozzle separately. The air moves through the nozzle under pressure and meets the liquid at the nozzle tip, causing the formation of spray droplets that are 30-60 microns in diameter.

The charge on droplets, through small pulls the spray towards the target at 75 times the force of gravity. The spray droplet can reverse direction, moves again gravity, to coat all sides of an object.

3. SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

A. General components

- Spray pump

In is a device used to spray a liquid. In agriculture, a spray pump is a piece of equipment that is used to apply herbicides, pesticides, and fertilizers on agriculture crops.

- Electrodes

Most frequently used material for electrode in electrostatic nozzle is Copper, Stainless Steel and Brass. For high voltage applications a new electrode material such as Nickel (200/201) forged bar is used for spray charging. Comparative study has made using different electrode materials electrode. For high voltage application Nickel is prefer. Appropriate and suitable electrode material may enhance the chargeability of finely divided particulate. Charge- to-mass-ratio varies for different material electrodes for a fixed applied voltage keeping other parameter constant. Therefore right material selection is important to work at lower potential to get higher charge-to-mass ratio and hence efficient spray system.

- High voltage circuit

High voltage circuit diagram and its layout is shown in above figure. Here we consider the diagram of stun gun by reducing stages on output side to get output as 1.5 Kv. A stun gun is gadget used to produce high voltage, low current signal. It usually powered by 12 volt battery. Here we design stun gun circuit using a IC 555 timer to produce a current fluctuating signal and voltage multiplier using a transformer and multiple stage arrangement of voltage doubles using capacitors and diodes.

- a) *Circuit Operating Principle*

The stun gun circuit is based on the principle behind a conventional stun gun. A 555 timer used to produce an oscillating signal of frequency determined by the external passive elements connected to timer. These low current electric pulses are fed to a step up transformer to produce high voltage signal, which is further increased by voltage multiplier circuit. The voltage multiplier circuit consists of multiple stages of voltage double which consist of two diodes and two capacitors. Output voltage is directly proportional to the number of stages.

- b) *Circuit Design*

Designing the circuit requires the pioneer step of deciding the output voltage. Here our requirement is to generate 1.4kv DC – 1.6kv DC from 400v.

From the equation,

$V_{out} = (2 * V_{in} + 1.414) * S$, where S is number of stages. for the output of 1400v-1600v Dc we required 3 stages, which is calculated by above formula.

- Battery

An electric battery is device consisting of one or more electromechanical cells with external connection .Approximately 12 volt rechargeable battery is used to give high voltage output. Lead acid battery is used.

4. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of electrostatic pesticide spraying is shown below. The block diagram shows hardware for electrostatic pesticide spray pump.

Electrostatic spray achieves a difficult target than uncharged spray with minimizing wastage and environmental impact from over dose and spray drift.

For designing air assisted nozzle following steps are following,

A. High voltage generation and droplet charging

Main aim in electrostatic spray system is droplet charging. Electrostatic induction based charging is prefer for agriculture pesticides applications. In electrostatic induction charging direct charge transfer to droplet formation zone of liquid jet results from electrostatic induction of electrons onto the continues jet and in order to maintain it at ground potential the presence of closely positioned electrode of positive polarity is required. Induction electrification process for droplet charging reducing the shock and hazardous to operate the nozzle system. In this 12V voltage can be boosted up to 1500V with booster.

B. Calculate charge to mass ratio

This ratio signifies the chargeability of the finely divided spray droplets by the charging electrode. To measure charge to mass ratio: Charge to mass ratio = Q/m mC/kg

Where is measured spray current (A) and Q_m is mass flow rate of liquid.

B. Check variation of charging of droplets with applied voltage.

C. Calculate flow rate of liquid and target distance.

5. MERITS

- With electrostatic spray deposition efficiency of pesticides is increases.
- It also increase the Bio-Efficiency i.e. less amount of pesticide require for maximum control of disease.
- Electrostatic spray achieve a difficult target than uncharged spray with minimize wastage and environmental impact from over dose spray drift.
- It also reduce the over spray , air pollution of environment.
- Quality of work is maintained with this concept.

6. DEMERITS

- Battery cycle time is limited.
- Battery charging system is required.

7. FUTURE SCOPE AND CHALLENGES

As summarized in the forgoing review, there have been significant advances in the research and development of electrostatic –spraying system technology for beneficial agriculture and biological applications throughout the 20th century .Important contributions to the underlying electrostatics science and the applied technology in this realm have been made worldwide by universities, industries, and technology governmental agencies. Solar energy can be extended for spraying pesticides, fertilizers, and fungicides

etc. Solar operated spray will help the farmers of those remote areas of country where fuel is not available easily. In this frame on top end a solar photovoltaic panel is fixed that converts solar power into electricity. This electricity is then provided to battery via a charging circuit.

8. RESULT

9. CONCLUSION

The topology with high voltage generation circuit is presented. High voltage generation circuit generates the voltage up to 1400 to 1600v DC, which is given to electrode and droplet got positively charged. It increases the deposition efficiency of pesticide comparison with conventional system. We observed that wastage of pesticide is reduced.

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